

THE ESSENCE OF TEACHING PRONUNCIATION OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE.

Madraximov Bexruz

Faculty of Foreign Philology, Termiz State University
Department of foreign language and literature

Abstract: Particular attention is paid to pronunciation, which is one of the components of language material. Because in order to express an opinion in a foreign language, it is necessary to pronounce and connect the sounds of the spoken sentence and to know the appropriate tone of speech (intonation). Pronunciation consists of three parts: hearing (acoustic), speaking (motor) and expressing meaning (semantic). Each language has its own performance feature.

Key words: Foreign language, pronunciation, phonetics, technological tools, methods, methods

Mastering the phonetic aspect of the language, mastering the skill of easy pronunciation is one of the important conditions of speech communication. The question arises whether it is possible to achieve perfect pronunciation in a foreign language in educational conditions. Methodists' answer is clear: students learn approximate (approximate) pronunciation in a foreign language (correct pronunciation can be learned in the mother tongue and in the second language). According to the idea of approximation, on the one hand, it is allowed to limit the volume of phonetic material and, on the other hand, the quality of the pronunciation of some sounds is lower than that of the native speaker. It is known that a certain foreign language sound causes a change in meaning, i.e. plays a phonemic role, so it is recommended to achieve a high approximation in its pronunciation, e.g. the shortness of the vowel sound in the English language, the sonority of the consonant sound at the end of the word, it is necessary to strive for high approximation, otherwise the content will be damaged. Approximation in pronunciation is determined, first of all, by the conditions of secondary education, that is, the artificial environment of learning a foreign language, and secondly, the pronunciation is complicated in relation to lexis and grammar.

Pronunciation of a foreign language relatively fluently and at a sufficient speed is the main requirement. This, firstly, ensures that the interlocutors understand each other, and secondly, it requires mastering the average speed of speech in a skillful way (it is known that the speed of speech in a foreign language means being able to say 110-150 words per minute : scientific experiments proved that 130-150 words are pronounced on average in English and French, and 110-130 words in German). In order for the student's speech to be understandable, he should learn not only the pronunciation

of sounds (phonemes) that express meaning, but also the basic tone (stress, weight, pause) of simple and compound sentences that are widely used.), melody) should also be mastered. So, pronunciation skills consist of articulation (saying) and intonation (speech tone) operations. Assuming that speech units exist only in sound symbols and that pronunciation is combined with lexical and grammatical skills, it is customary to acquire them as a whole in speech. Pronunciation skill is understood as an integral linguistic action that ensures the realization of a speech unit through the appropriate sounds. The question of which classes or educational stages to teach foreign language pronunciation has been the cause of various disputes. Separating a separate class or stage was contrary to the logic of the methodology. Because mastering pronunciation depends on speech skills and abilities. The content of educational and methodological tools created for a particular school realizes the distribution of the pronunciation minimum in its own way. However, as a general rule for all schools, the following order is accepted: most of the sounds are presented in the initial period of education, in the middle level, new sound combinations, stress and intonation continue to be taught, in the middle or upper level, all development of skills in relation to pronunciation phenomena, therefore, work on formation of pronunciation skills is carried out from the beginning to the end of foreign language teaching. Listening-pronunciation skills are formed while learning lexicon and grammar from language materials.

Foreign language phonetic (pronunciation) minimum! It is selected depending on the lexical and grammatical minimums. Linguistic material usually consists of active and passive minima. At the minimum of phonetics (pronunciation), the concepts of active and passive are interpreted a little differently. Active and passive pronunciation minima are studied at the same time. They are part of complex speech skills and are manifested in speaking (speech-pronunciation skills) and perceptual understanding (listening skills) aspects of oral speech. Active and passive pronunciation minima differ as follows: approximation is allowed in the active minima, and such a situation is not encountered in the passive. Work is done on the limited phonetic material within the active minimum of pronunciation, and variants of the studied foreign language phonemes are also found in the passive. Pronunciation minimum for certain types of educational institutions, e.g. for secondary schools, it is common regardless of the language experience of your students. For example, the sounds, sound combinations, phonetic phenomena and intonation structure of the studied foreign language constitute the minimum of pronunciation. (It will be proved below that it is contrary to the methodological logic that some researchers do not include the minimum units of foreign language pronunciation units in the student's mother tongue (or language experience).)

It is inevitable that all phonetic units in the lexical-grammatical material of a foreign language will take place in the pronunciation minimum. But it is also known in the methodology that pronunciation units that are easy to learn are not specially taught in separate exercises, because they are not part of the content of teaching pronunciation. Therefore, the minimum language experience is not taken into account, and in the content of teaching pronunciation, events that require special time and effort to master due to special difficulty are collected. The criterion of the norm of pronunciation is close to the criterion of style and serves as a measure of not including the dialectal (dialectal) pronunciation to the phonetic minimum. It is recommended to study literary pronunciation, which is a phonetic example. The widespread criterion is similar to style and normativity. Phonetic units that are widely used in speech are selected and included in the pronunciation minimum. According to these selection criteria, the pronunciation minimum is selected from the phonetic system of the studied foreign language. The phonetic features of a foreign language are taken into account when following the criteria.

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